

Time, Truth and Madness in 20th Century Literature Taking Into Account Faulkner's "The Sound and The Fury," and O'Neill's, "Long Day's Journey Into Night"

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ABSTRACT: The harshest reality or truth attached with life since the day Adam was banished from heaven is that man has been confined in time. Each one of us is chained by the hands of clocks. We are unable to freeze our moments of joy and also cannot erase our terrible past. The dilemma of modern man is that he wants to achieve more in less time. Also, when he is unable to get the desire to be completely satisfied with the life he becomes frustrated and a shadow of madness circles over him. This paper has illuminated the tragedy of a modern man. The concept of *Truth, Time and Madness* is explained through literary texts namely, "*The Sound and the Fury*," by William Faulkner and Eugene O'Neill's famous play, "*Long Day's Journey into Night*." The paper has also drawn parallels between treatment of themes, common motifs, structure and language.

KEYWORDS: Truth, Time and Madness